

A New Ensemble Demand Forecasting System for Online Retail Price Elasticity

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Abstract

As the world's largest retailer, Walmart's core mission is to provide low-priced products with high quality, so that our customers can enjoy their lives better. Walmart e-Commerce demonstrates a rapidly growing share of consumer spending which in turn generates large data sets about the demand and dynamic pricing of a wide variety of products. It has been observed that online customers may present different shopping behavior, including different levels of price sensitivity, compared to those at off-line market. The price sensitivity increases the importance of the e-Commerce price elasticity of demand, which is defined as the percent change in demand caused by a percent change in price. As a result, an accurate and immediate price elasticity is necessary for the success of implementing e-Commerce pricing strategies.

In this research, we propose an ensemble-based forecasting system, which applies machine learning techniques to the rich daily sales data from Walmart e-Commerce and generates price elasticity score for making pricing decisions in a timely manner. The proposed ensemble system consists of three models: Bayesian Structural Time Series (BSTS) Model, Time Decay Model (TDM), and Robust Linear Model (RLM). Based on the testing results, this system evaluates multiple business metrics under different price adjustments, which significantly improves the capability to predict future sales units, revenue, and profit for each product at various price points levels, and further supports us on more intelligent dynamic online pricing decisions.

Key Words: Price Elasticity, Ensemble System, Time Series, Forecasting

1. Introduction

Leveraging the advantage of about 4700 traditional retail stores in USA, Walmart e-Commerce business is expanding and growing rapidly. The thriving e-Commerce platform generates lots of data from many dimensions, which makes utilizing such data in supporting our business decisions an attention-grabbing topic for Walmart.

Every Day Low Price (EDLP) is well-known as the cornerstone of Walmart pricing strategy, and our price focus has never been stronger. Implementing such strategy indicates Walmart's interest on increasing the demand and revenue by keeping a competitive low price for all the products on both off-line and on-line platforms. Naturally, an accurate price elasticity of demand, which measures the percent change in demand caused by a percent change in price, is one of the key factors in making pricing decisions.

Customer's shopping patterns may not be identical over different platforms. Hence exploring the price elasticity of the online demand is crucial for a successful implementation of EDLP strategy on our online platform Walmart.com. Such information enables an accurate forecast on multiple business metrics including revenue and profit for different level of price points. In this work, we propose an ensemble demand forecasting system based on daily e-Commerce sales data and machine learning methods to produce a dynamic and precise price elasticity for decision making.

1.1 Related Work

Demand forecasting and analyzing the sensitivity of demand over price changes have been an active area of research. Researchers have been using it to achieve a variety of goals, including pricing optimization, revenue management, optimal budget allocation, etc. To achieve price optimization, Gupta and Pathak generated user group level pricing by first creating user segments using K-means clustering, and then using a linear regression model to allocate a price range for each cluster [3]. Using the prior results of user cluster and price range, they attempted to determine customer's propensity to purchase a particular product. In order to generate the propensity, they used a logistic regression model which predicts the likelihood of a user group purchasing a particular product within the earlier identified price range. Their experiment was conducted on repeat customers where they concluded that the framework generates better revenue.

To tackle the Price Investment task in offline markets (stores), Mehrotra et al. proposed a framework for generating price recommendations so to maximize the demand volume or lift for each of the products [6]. This work focused on solving the Price Investment task for products within Food and Consumables department, where they formalize the objective as two sub-problems:

1. Determine the best way to distribute/allocate entire budget among all product categories.
2. Generate the best price recommendation for each product under each category.

For the first sub-problem, optimization has been applied to determine the discount level for each category such that the total anticipated investment is almost equal to the budget allotted and revenue matches the expectation. A Bayesian structural time series (BSTS) [8] demand forecasting model was used to produce category level demand, which was a pre-requisite for the optimization problem, where modeling was carried out at the item-week level within a single price market. The results were then aggregated to the category-quarter level and fed to the optimization system, which generates the discount rate to be used within each category. The second sub-problem was solved by doing constrained optimization and utilizing the investment distribution identified from the first sub-problem. In this optimization, the focus was on maximizing the total revenue for a category subjecting to the pre-specified investment constraints.

On similar lines, Liu and Sustik built a system that predicts demand and revenue at a given price point [5]. In order to find the optimal price, they formulated a revenue maximization problem over discrete finite time horizon and discrete prices. Daily level long-term trend, seasonality, current sales, and certain explanatory features were taken into account while modeling the demand.

1.2 Proposed System Architecture

The proposed e-Commerce Ensemble Elasticity system in Walmart e-Commerce is comprised of the following components (Figure 1):

1. A daily-refreshed data loader, which loads the most recently updated Walmart.com sales data into the system.
2. A data pre-processor, which performs standard data cleaning procedures and normalization.

3. An ensemble price elasticity model trainer, which consists three data pipelines to train the elasticity models. These Three pipelines each forecasts the demand over certain back-test period for all items, and the one with the smallest MAPE¹ will be selected for each item.
4. A forecasting application, which forecasts item’s demand by using price coefficients or model configuration, computes unit lift, revenue and profit at various prices level (discounts or premiums), and finally generates the estimated price elasticity for each item.

Figure 1: Architecture Diagram

2. System Framework

In this study, we developed an ensemble forecasting system that links three independent models concurrently to enhance the estimation of future price elasticity for e-Commerce items. Such multi-model ensemble system allows us to exploit the diversity of skillful predictions from different models and utilize the merits across the candidate models [2]. Although we present three selected models in current ensemble system, the system structure is compatible with other models and can be easily extended with additional suitable models.

This ensemble system is designed to improve forecasting accuracy comparing to a single-model based forecasting. Although each model within the ensemble system may be influenced by some extreme input, the whole system is found to be fault tolerant hence can substantially minimize errors in the final output. Comparing with each single constituent model, both model diversity and accuracy have been improved by using our ensemble system for making predictions. In this work, the proposed ensemble system consists of three distinct models: Bayesian Structural Time Series (BSTS [8]) Model, Time Decay Model (TDM [1]), and Robust Linear Model (RLM [4]). Model Diversity has been taken into consideration as BSTS captures the time-series features, TDM focus more on the recent data that is close to the forecasting time-period, and RLM is more robust to extreme outliers. Model selection is performed by picking the model with the smallest MAPE when more than one models have valid outputs for the same item. The generated elasticity score is considered as ‘accurate’ if MAPE is under a predetermined cutoff. The novel ensemble system can benefit from all the advantages of the three models.

We evaluate the performance of this ensemble system by demonstrating its ‘accurate elasticity coverage’, which is defined as the percentage of items (or sales amount) with valid accurate elasticity score.

¹ Mean Absolute Percentage Error, set a certain value as the cutoff of ‘accuracy’.

2.1 Data Preprocessing

All of products on Walmart.com have a multi-layer product hierarchy. In this work, the initial data of historical daily transaction and product information are both sourced at item level, which is the fine-grained granular level that can be further grouped into categories and departments later. For the daily aggregated data, we consider a weighted daily price which is calculated by weighting the transaction price with its sales in the same day. Some dummy variables are created to record the holiday/weekend information and item's transactability. For instance, if a transaction happens at a national holiday or a weekend, the dummy variable is set to be 1, otherwise 0.

In this work, we have randomly selected high-sales products with enough long sales history and price volatility across 6 major departments. The data with 12-month time horizon is used in modeling, where the first 11-month data is used for training and the last 1-month data is used for backtesting. The following month data is used for forecasting test (independent testing).

2.2 Model Architecture

2.2.1 BSTS

The framework of Bayesian Structural Time Series (BSTS [8]) is defined by the state equation (1) and transition equation (2).

The observation equation relates the observed data y_t to a vector of latent variables α_t known as the 'state',

$$y_t = Z_t^T \alpha_t + \epsilon_t, \quad (1)$$

and the transition equation describes how the latent state evolves through time,

$$\alpha_{t+1} = T_t \alpha_t + R_t \eta_t, \quad (2)$$

where the error terms $\epsilon_t \stackrel{i.i.d.}{\sim} N(0, \sigma_{\epsilon_t})$ and $\eta_t \stackrel{iid}{\sim} N(0, \sigma_{\eta_t})$. The arrays Z_t, T_t, R_t are structural parameters. They might contain parameters in the statistical sense, but often they simply contain strategically placed 0's and 1's indicating which bits of α_t are relevant for a particular computation.

In the proposed system, BSTS pipeline executes at an item level, as we train the model for each item to forecast its demand at multiple price points. One of the main advantages of BSTS is the flexibility of customizing the components for each time series. In the current setup, we have used three BSTS configurations which consist of four different components such as random walk, seasonality, local linear trend and auto-regressive to capture the volatility of sale units on the training time horizon. Any input parameters which are required for each of the component within a configuration are calculated from respective time series using multiple statistical tests.

Our model has considered many sparse features as input. To achieve better feature selection, Spike and Slab priors have been used as prior to the regression coefficients. Spike represents the inclusion probability of the features whereas Slab encodes our prior expectations about the feature coefficients.

Once the prior is developed, with the given model parameters we draw samples from the latent states and the time series components using MCMC and simulate the posterior distribution of the data [7].

2.2.2 RLM

Robust Linear Model (RLM [4]) is linear regression based on M-estimation². It is similar to maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) but using robust ψ function which is the gradient of the robust likelihood function $\rho(x_i, \theta)$.

The price elasticity can be considered as a continuous variable and can be estimated using M-estimation. In this study, we use RLM instead of least squares regression to deal with the outlier issues. The retail data likely contains outliers or high leverage data at some points or the other, but it is risky to exclude all of them in data analysis, which often produces wrong inference. Robust regression could be a good strategy to deal with those outliers as it is a compromise between minimizing the influence of these points in the analysis and including all the data points without too much data manipulation. The idea of robust regression is to weigh the observations differently based on how well behaved these observations are. Generally speaking, it is a form of weighted or re-weighted least squares regression.

In the current system, we use asymmetric Huber ψ weight with higher penalty for positive value, which is rare for elasticity. Weight is 1 for x in predefined interval and quickly reduce outside of the interval with positive value reducing at higher rate.

We use Huber's ψ for M-estimation,

$$\hat{\theta} = \underset{\theta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{i=1}^n \rho(x_i, \theta), \quad (3)$$

where $\rho(x_i, \theta)$ is the robust likelihood function with the i^{th} item's percentage change in price x_i and the price elasticity θ .

2.2.3 TDM

Assuming demand sensitivity that occurred in the distant past is less significant than the ones occurred close to the forecast time period, the time decay model (TDM [1]) gives more weight to historical data that is closer to the forecasting period.

In this model, we assume the price elasticity is subject to exponential decay if it decreases at a rate proportional to its reference value. Mathematically, this process can be expressed by equation (4),

$$\frac{dN(t)}{dt} = -\lambda N(t) \quad (4)$$

where $N(t)$ is the quantity at time t and λ is a positive rate called the exponential decay constant. By separating variables and integral both sides, the solution to this equation is:

$$N(t) = N_0 e^{-\lambda t},$$

where $N_0 = N(0)$ is the initial quantity, that is, the quantity at time $t = 0$. The decay rate can be measured using mean-lifetime and half-life method. The mean lifetime method assumes that the decaying quantity, $N(t)$, is the weighted average value of historical price elasticity in our data set. We compute the average length of time that a price elasticity remains in our data. In the mean

² MLE-type estimation.

lifetime method, the exponential time constant, τ , is the reverse of the decay rate λ : $\tau = \frac{1}{\lambda}$. Then the price elasticity at t is: $N_t = N_0 e^{-t/\tau}$.

The half-life assumes that the exponential decay is mean (median) of its initial value. The half-life is often denoted by the symbol $t_{0.5}$ and can be calculated using $t_{0.5} = \frac{\ln(2)}{\lambda}$. When this expression is inserted for τ in the exponential equation above, and $\ln(2)$ is absorbed into the base, this equation becomes,

$$N(t) = N_0 2^{-t/t_{0.5}}. \quad (5)$$

2.3 Model and System Evaluation

The ensemble system uses three pipelines to generate elasticity scores for the same item, and the one with the smallest MAPE is considered as the final output. The MAPE measures the relative statistical distance between the actual value and the forecasted value. The MAPE of each item is calculated by aggregating the units over the backtest (or forecast) time interval and expressed as $|A_i - F_i|/A_i$, where A_i is the total actual sales units of the i th item in this period and F_i is the forecast value of the i th item in the same period. Hence, the MAPE on the category level could be computed by

$$\text{Category MAPE} = \frac{100\%}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \left| \frac{A_i - F_i}{A_i} \right|, \quad (6)$$

where m is the total item number in this category. Note that the ensemble system generates only one elasticity score per item. Hence, a single model's accuracy may be slightly higher than its performance in the system but much lower than the accuracy of the ensemble system. Here, the system accuracy is measured by the percentage of the 'accurate' ones at different granularity level.

Table 1 reports the number (%) of items contributed by each model to the accurate results in the backtesting stage and the forecasting stage. In a total of 982 items with predicted results during the backtesting, TDM contributes 355 (36.15%) results with the lowest MAPE as compared to the other two, RLM contributes 138 (14.05%), and BSTS contributes 489 (49.80%). Based on the model pipeline, we use the model-selected price coefficient or model configuration of the 982 items to forecast their sales units in the forecasting stage. Out of the 691 items with predicted results during the forecasting stage, TDM contributes 268 (38.78%) results with the lowest MAPE comparing with the other two, RLM contributes 77 (11.14%), and BSTS contribute 346 (50.07%).

Table 2 compares the accuracy of TDM, RLM and BSTS at the backtesting stage, the forecasting stage, and the overall performance. Let N be the total item number loading into the system, b_n be the total accurate item number in the backtest stage, f_n be the total accurate item number in both backtest stage and forecasting stage. The overall accurate rate of is 70.37% in the backtest stage, 71.49% in the forecast stage. We also calculate the real accuracy which is backtest accuracy multiply forecast accuracy.

Figure (2a) shows the distributions of MAPE by model. TDM has the lowest median MAPE of 0.17, while RLM has the largest median MAPE of 0.25. Figure (2b) presents the distributions of MAPE in the forecast stage and the median MAPE for TDM, RLM and BSTS are 0.16, 0.19 and 0.17, respectively.

Table 3 demonstrates the performance of the ensemble system in some selected categories. The 'Actual Unit Change' column shows the percentage change between the total actual sales units in

the forecast time period and the total actual sale units in the backtest time period within the category. The 'Predicted Unit Change' column is the percentage change between the total predicted sales units in the forecast time period and the total actual sale units within the backtest time period. The 'Category MAPE' is the mean of MAPEs of all items in the category. The 'Ave. Discount' is the average price discount/premium at which the category achieves the highest profit (or lowest loss). The 'Items Coverage' shows the percentage of item numbers with accurate forecast results in the category level and the 'Sales Coverage' shows the percentage of item sales with accurate forecast results in the category level.

Table 1: Model Contribution in the System

Model	Backtest Contribution	Forecast Contribution
TDM	355 (36.15%)	268 (38.78%)
RLM	138 (14.05%)	77 (11.14%)
BSTS	489 (49.80%)	346 (50.07%)
Overall	982 (100.00%)	691 (100.00%)

Table 2: Model Performance in the System

Model	Backtest Accuracy, b_n/N (%)	Forecast Accuracy, f_n/b_n (%)	Real Accuracy, f_n/N (%)
TDM	268/355 (75.49%)	196/268 (73.13%)	196/355 (55.21%)
RLM	77/138 (55.80%)	51/77 (66.23%)	51/138 (36.96%)
BSTS	346/489 (70.76%)	247/346 (71.39%)	247/489 (50.51%)
Overall	691/982 (70.37%)	494/691 (71.49%)	494/982 (50.31%)

Table 3: Performance of System in Some Selected Categories

Category (anonymized)	Actual Unit Change (%)	Predicted Unit Change (%)	Category MAPE	Ave. Discount (%)	Item Coverage (%)	Sales Coverage (%)
A	-10.18	-4.61	0.09	8.8	59.09	78.72
B	73.33	82.86	0.03	5.0	56.66	67.79
C	-9.38	-10.10	0.10	13.6	62.66	72.97
D	-24.92	-27.61	0.14	8.0	58.99	84.66
E	-33.33	-32.71	0.12	8.3	72.13	96.82
F	-12.05	-0.64	0.14	12.1	67.11	82.91
G	-0.17	4.51	0.13	7.90	61.11	66.50
H	-18.75	-13.54	0.06	10.0	51.88	66.87
I	-22.27	-17.95	0.12	12.5	61.96	67.08

Figure 2: Boxplots of Backtest and Forecast MAPE

Figure 3: Revenue & Profit Changes versus Price Changes

2.4 Application of Ensemble Price Elasticity System

Using the elasticity corresponding to the best performance (minimum MAPE) in the forecasting stage, we can predict the changes in unit, revenue, and profit under different price changes. Figure (3a) and (3b) shows the changes of each item in revenue and profit, respectively, under different discount or premium percentage of price. Different color in Figure (3a) and (3b) represents different category of product. Figure (3a) shows that the price decrease (-20% to -5%) lowers the revenue of most of items sold online, but the price increase most likely raises the revenue. However, the profit of most of items will have the opposite changes in response to price adjustment. Figure (3b) shows that the price discount will result in loss for most of items. The merchants can apply the predicted revenue and profit to predict how to adjust the price and how that price change will affect the overall revenue and profit.

3. Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, we designed an ensemble system to predict the price elasticity for Walmart e-Commerce to improve the decision on their price adjustment. Using the historical daily online sales data, our ensemble price elasticity system is applying TDM, RLM, and BSTS model to estimate the item level price elasticity. In the backtest stage, the system evaluates the accuracy of each model and select the elasticity with the smallest MAPE. In the forecasting stage, the system uses the price coefficients or model configuration from backtest to predict the sales units, revenue, and profit for each item at different prices. The timely and accurately predicted price elasticity will help the merchants of e-Commerce to understand how the revenue and profit will change under different price adjustment. The proposed system could be a crucial tool for the implementation of EDLP strategy to Walmart's e-Commerce.

In future, we will try to improve the precision of the current ensemble system. First, we'll try to include some macroeconomic indicators, such as consumer price index and unemployment rate, as features to accommodate for the potential impact of economic environments. Second, more candidate models can be considered into the ensemble system, such as robust Poisson model that can be used for the items with low sales. Finally, new statistical criteria, e.g., new relative distance instead of MAPE, will be discussed to deal with the data sparseness issue in the e-Commerce data.

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